

Modifying an existing automotive (IC) air conditioning system for DC power

Abstract— This paper describes the design and implementation of a system that uses a DC-powered electric air conditioning (AC) compressor instead of the conventional engine-driven AC compressor found in vehicles with internal combustion engines. The proposed system uses thermoelectric generators (TEGs) and solar panels as the energy source. It is designed for use by many people in Sri Lanka. A LiFePO₄ battery stores energy, which provides sufficient power to operate and power the electric compressor without the involvement of the engine. The project demonstrates that adding such a system to current vehicles is feasible, cost-effective, and environmentally beneficial.

Keywords— electric compressor, solar vehicle retrofit, thermoelectric generator, sustainable automotive design

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

At present, the automobile manufacturing sector is focused on producing products in an environmentally friendly manner. In other words, electric cars are produced in large quantities to minimize environmental pollution and reduce fuel consumption. The air-conditioning system of the current internal combustion engines consumes a large amount of fuel. This is because the compressor of the air conditioning system works by using a belt with the damper wheel of the engine. As this process causes a large amount of fuel consumption and emission, the idea is to create this project using the currently used solar energy and kinetic energy.

The design in this project intends to use renewable energy sources using solar power and kinetic energy generated by the rear wheels of the vehicle to run the compressor separately from the engine. Here, solar panels are attached to the roof of the car. The energy from the car's wheels is converted into a regenerative braking system to store energy. The energy produced is stored and used to operate the AC compressor. This electric compressor uses 12V-24V volts.

The main problem solved by this project is to reduce the load on the engine by using sustainability and energy in the process and using renewable energy to reduce emissions. We hope that this project will help to move automotive technology towards a green technology.

B. Statement of Problem

A common challenge faced by vehicle users in Sri Lanka is the additional fuel consumption caused by the vehicle's air conditioning (AC) system.

Some of the main problems identified by this method are:

- Fuel Consumption Due to AC Usage
- In internal combustion engine vehicles, the AC compressor is connected to the engine and runs, which increases fuel consumption. This is a well-understood fact for consumers. Due to the rising fuel prices in Sri Lanka, many drivers are avoiding using AC, as not doing so would be a very expensive proposition.

- Lack of alternative energy sources for vehicles

Currently, there is no evidence of renewable energy sources such as solar power or waste heat recovery for vehicles in Sri Lanka. A large amount of waste heat is released through the exhaust manifold of a car, which can be used to generate electricity, and such a method is not currently available.

- Environmental impact of fuel

AC compressors increase fuel consumption. This increases CO₂ emissions, which are a greenhouse gas, and has an impact on the environment.

- Usability in hot weather

Sri Lanka has high temperatures and humidity, so it is impossible to avoid using the AC system to save energy. Therefore, the use of AC is essential for comfort.

- Economic burden on used vehicle owners

This is a great help in improving the fuel efficiency of used vehicles as most Sri Lankans cannot afford the latest hybrid or electric vehicles.

It is cost-effective to design such a vehicle using renewable sources. The reason is that the purchase of expensive hybrid or electric vehicles is not affordable for the middle class in Sri Lanka.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Modification Process

To implement this system, several major modifications are made to the selected car, including the removal of the traditional AC compressor, the integration of an electric AC compressor, and the installation of solar panels, thermal power generators, and a battery system.

Removing the AC compressor connected to the engine:

- Removing the AC compressor from the engine, which is connected to the pulley and belt.
- Reshaped and connected the refrigerant pipes to fit the new electric AC compressor.
- Check and ensure that other components in the space are not disturbed at the end of the installation.

Installing the Electric AC Compressor:

- Select a 12V or 48V electric AC compressor based on power requirements.
- Securely mount the compressor in the engine bay or in a suitable location.
- Test and connect new refrigerant lines to the evaporator and condenser.
- Install a good wiring system to operate the compressor from the battery..

B. Integration of Renewable Energy Sources

To generate sufficient electrical energy, two renewable energy sources are used: solar panels and thermoelectric generators (TEGs).

Installing Flexible Solar Panels:

- Flexible thin film solar panels are chosen because of their lightweight and adaptable nature.
- Clean the roof of car and prepare it for panel attachment.
- Install the solar panels using strong adhesive or mounting tools.
- Electrical connections are made to a charge controller to regulate the voltage.
- Connect the charge controller to the battery system to store enough energy.

Installation of thermoelectric generators:

- Selection of TEG capable of withstanding high temperatures (150°-300°).
- Cleaning the exhaust manifold where the TEG will be installed.
- Applying heat-resistant thermal paste to improve heat transfer.
- Regulating the power generated by this TEG with a DC-DC converter and storing it in the battery.

C. Choosing the Right Battery

A suitable battery is essential for storing the energy generated by solar panels and TEG.

Choosing the Battery:

- It is advisable to choose a lithium-ion battery for high energy density and efficiency.
- Calculate the battery capacity based on the power demand of the compressor and the energy generation by the above methods.
- Install a small battery management system (BMS) to control overcharging and prevent deep discharge.

Installing the Battery:

- Connect the battery to a safe and ventilated place inside the car.
- Connect a good insulator to protect the battery from excessive heat.
- Make the electrical connections between the battery, charge controller and compressor.

D. Electrical System Design

An efficient electrical system is essential for the proper operation of this system.

Wiring and Circuit Protection:

- High-quality heat-resistant wires are used to connect all components.
- Installation of circuit breakers to prevent electrical breakdowns.
- Setting up the control system for energy management:
- Energy generation and battery status can be monitored using a smart controller.
- The system automatically switches between solar panels and TEG power as needed.

III. DESIGN

The aim of this project is to improve the fuel efficiency of the vehicle by using renewable energy sources to power an electric AC compressor.

Fig. 1. Design Maruti Suzuki Alto K10

A. Evolution and selection of conceptual designs (Final designing)

As a continuation of the conceptual design, the following two energy sources are combined to generate electricity for an electric AC compressor:

Fig. 2. Solar panel system (roof mounted)

Fig. 3. Thermal Electric Generators (TEGs) (Exhaust manifold mounted)

B. Designed for mounting solar panels on roofs and bonnets

Type of solar panels:

Flexible monocrystalline solar panels were selected to avoid adding excess weight to the roof and bonnet.

Being flexible, they can be easily installed on the curved roof of the car.

Placement on the roof and bonnet:

According to the calculations, the available surface area to cover the entire roof with flexible solar panels is approximately 1.2m². Of this amount, 0.6m² was covered.

The panels are arranged in lightweight aluminum frames to minimize wind resistance.

The cables for connecting the battery and power management system are routed through the roof posts and connected.

C. Positioning of thermoelectric generators (TEG) on the exhaust manifold

When selecting TEG modules, Bismuth Telluride (Bi_2Te_3) is suitable for high temperature waste heat recovery.

Positioning in the exhaust system:

The best location is near the mufflers and catalytic converters.

To maintain temperature differences and increase efficiency, the cold side is installed downwards. When the vehicle is moving, the air flow is good. This

Proper ventilation and airflow prevent the TEG from overheating.

Wiring:

The wires are connected to the power management system via heat-resistant cables from the exhaust system to the battery.

Since the output voltage is low, a DC-DC converter is installed to increase the voltage.

Installing:

REG can be securely mounted using a custom metal bracket made of stainless steel.

Fig. 4. Conceptual design of TEGs installed in mufflers and catalytic converters

D. Selection of electric AC compressor and installation in the right location

Here, a 12V electric AC compressor was selected. The cooling capacity of the selected vehicle is 2kW. Therefore, an AC compressor under a suitable brand name was selected for it.

It is best to place it near the engine bay of the vehicle. This should be securely mounted to the chassis in a shock-resistant manner.

Fig. 5. Conceptual design of the location where the electric compressors should be installed

E. Battery Selection and Placement

Here, choosing the 12V 100Ah LiFePO_4 battery can provide a long life. (2000-5000 cycles).

- This is very suitable due to its high efficiency and fast charging.
- This battery is enough to operate the AC for a proper time.
- The best place to place the battery in the vehicle is the passenger seat.
- The reason is to keep the center of gravity low and
- Excessive heat near the engine bay is harmful.
- Reduces the space effect in the cabin.
- This has some impact on fuel efficiency as there is additional weight reduction.

Fig. 6. Conceptual design of where the battery should be installed

F. Design calculations

Below are the calculations required for the solar panel system and thermal electric generators (TEGs) to calculate the total energy generation to power the electric AC compressor.

Solar panel system design calculation:

Fig. 7. Dimensions of the solar system to be installed on the vehicle

There are two solar panels on the roof,

Panel length; 974 mm.

Panel width: 407 mm.

Panel Area:

$$A_{panel,roof} = 974 \times 407 = 396,218 \text{ mm}^2 = 0.396 \text{ m}^2$$

Total roof solar panel area:

$$A_{total,roof} = 2 \times 0.396 = 0.792 \text{ m}^2$$

There are two solar panels on the bonnet,

Panel length: 784 mm.

Panel width: 598 mm.

$$A_{panel,bonnet} = 784 \times 598 = 468,832 \text{ mm}^2 = 0.469 \text{ m}^2$$

Total roof solar panel area:

$$A_{total,bonnet} = 2 \times 0.469 = 0.938 \text{ m}^2$$

Total solar panel area on the car:

$$A_{total,bonnet} = A_{total,roof} + A_{total,bonnet} = 0.792 + 0.938 = 1.73 \text{ m}^2$$

Thermal power generation system design calculation:

Fig. 8. The number of TEGs to be installed in the vehicle

Exhaust manifold dimension,

Length: 660 mm.

Width: 324 mm.

Total area:

$$A_{manifold} = 660 \times 324 = 213,840 \text{ mm}^2 = 0.214 \text{ m}^2$$

TEG Size and Placement,

Each TEG Module: 40 mm × 40 mm

Number of TEGs in Exhaust Manifold: 66

Number of TEGs in Catalytic Converter: 4

Total Number of TEGs: 66 + 4 = 70

Total area occupied by TEGs:

$$A_{TEG} = 70 \times (40 \times 40) = 70 \times 1600 = 112,000 \text{ mm}^2 = 0.112 \text{ m}^2$$

Spacing between mounted TEGs: Calculations include a 15 mm spacing.

G. System components and wiring in the diagram

A diagrammatic design of the connection of solar panels, thermal power generators, battery storage, and an electric AC compressor are shown below.

Fig. 9. System components and wiring in the diagram

IV. MATERIAL

The materials and cost analysis for creating this project includes only essential components, making the design simple and affordable.

A. Solar panel, TEG & Others system

Component	Material
Flexible Monocrystalline Solar Panel	Silicon, polymer
TEG Modules (40mm × 40mm, 5W each, Bi ₂ Te ₃)	Bismuth Telluride (Bi ₂ Te ₃)
MPPT Charge controller(12V, 20A)	
LiFePO ₄ Battery (12V, 50Ah)	Lithium Iron Phosphate
Battery Management System (BMS, 12V, 50A)	pcb
Electric Compressor (12V, 2.0kW Cooling)	Aluminum, Copper
High-Temperature Wiring (TEG to Battery)	Copper
Mounting Brackets	Stainless Steel
Fuses & Circuit Breakers	Copper

Materials

B. Final cost analysis

Final Cost Estimate: 301490/=

This amount is not a fixed amount, but the cost can be reduced by installing a used AC compressor.

Expected power output of solar and TEG system: 400W max. Sustainable energy projects for AC operations are cost effective.

By reducing unnecessary components, this design can be further simplified.

V. CALCULATION & RESULTS

A. Solar power generation

Solar Panel Efficiency Assumption

Efficiency of flexible monocrystalline solar panel: 18% (0.18)

Average solar irradiance value at noon in Sri Lanka: 1000 W/m²

Total solar panel area: 1.73 m²

Power Output:

$$P_{solar} = A_{total\ solar} * Efficiency * Solar\ Irradiance$$

$$P_{solar} = 1.73 * 0.18 * 1000$$

$$P_{solar} = 311.4W$$

B. TEG Power Generation

Temperature difference

Hot side temperature (mufflers): 300°C

Cold side temperature (air cooling): 80°C

Temperature Difference (ΔT): $\Delta T = 300 - 80 = 220^\circ C$

Power Output Per Bi₂Te₃ TEG Module

At $\Delta T = 220^\circ C$, a TEG module has an average power output of 5w. (It is given by the manufacturer)

TEG 70 Total Power: $P_{TEG} = 70 * 5 = 350W$

C. Total energy generation

Sources	Power output
Solar panels	311W
TEGs system	350W
Total Power output	661W

Energy Generation

D. Energy storage and utilization

Steps in charging a battery

LiFePO₄ 12V, 100Ah (~1200Wh Capacity)

Energy required for full charge: 1200 Wh

Battery charging time from solar panels and TEG

$$Time = \frac{Battery\ Capacity}{Total\ power\ output} = \frac{1200}{661} = 1.8\ hours$$

This battery charges for about 1.8 hours.

E. Power consumption by AC compressors

Electric Compressor: 500W

Fully charged battery runtime:

$$Time = \frac{1200Wh}{500W} = 2.4\ hours$$

- The battery takes about 2 hours to charge while driving.
- The battery is fully charged during the normal driving time.
- The additional energy generated can extend the AC run time to over 2 hours.

VI. CONCLUSION

• System Feasibility

The system generates enough power to operate the electric AC compressor independently of the engine and the battery is fully charged in 2 hours. At least 2 hours of AC operation can be guaranteed.

• Environmental and Economic Benefits

This significantly reduces fuel consumption, which is beneficial for used car owners in Sri Lanka.

Reduces CO₂ emissions, promoting green car technology.

• Challenges and Future Optimization

As cloudy conditions can limit efficiency, additional battery capacity or alternative power sources should be explored going forward.

TEG efficiency improvements include the use of better heat sinks.

After adding battery and power components, it is essential to properly maintain the load on the vehicle.

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